

Encapsulation of 3,5-dihydroxybenzoic acid and 3,4,5-trihydroxybenzoic acid by α - and β -cyclodextrins : Spectral and theoretical studies

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Abstract : Inclusion complex formation of α -CD, β -CD, hydroxy propyl- α -CD (Hp- α -CD) and hydroxy propyl- β -CD (Hp- β -CD) of 3,5-dihydroxybenzoic acid (DHBA) and 3,4,5-trihydroxybenzoic acid (THBA) were investigated. The inclusion complexes of both guest molecules with the four CDs were analysed by UV-Visible, steady state and time resolved fluorescence, FTIR, ^1H NMR and PM3 methods. The results shows (i) in pH \sim 1, pH \sim 7 and pH \sim 10 solutions both HBAs form 1 : 1 inclusion complex, (ii) the entrapment of both HBAs in the four CDs cause ICT emission at pH \sim 1 and pH \sim 7 and (iii) at pH \sim 10, the hydroxyl anion and IPT prevents ICT emission. PM3 results indicate that dianion : CD complex is significantly more favorable than the others complexes. The geometry of the most stable complex shows that the hydroxyl group is entrapped in the interior part of the CD and carboxyl group is present in the hydrophilic part of the CD cavity in DHBA. In THBA, the carboxyl group is entrapped in the interior part of the CD and hydroxyl group is present in the hydrophilic part of the CD cavity.

Keywords : Cyclodextrin, 3,5-dihydroxybenzoic acid, 3,4,5-trihydroxybenzoic acid, inclusion complex, molecular modeling.

Introduction

Cyclodextrins (CD) are water-soluble, cyclic oligosaccharides which form hydrophobic cavities with hydrophilic external walls¹⁻³. The ability of CD's to accommodate guest molecules of the appropriate size in their cavities has been utilized by many investigators to control the photophysical and photochemical properties such as fluorescence enhancement⁴⁻⁶ intramolecular excimer/exciple formation^{7,8} and photoisomerization^{9,10} of some organic molecules. Nag *et al.*¹¹ have demonstrated that the twisted intramolecular charge transfer (TICT) emission of 4-(*N,N*-dimethylamino)benzonitrile (DMABN) is enhanced on complexation with α -CD. They have attributed this property to the reduced polarity rather than to the restricted molecular motion inside the CDs cavities. As the polarity decreases, the energy gap between the ICT state and the Franck-Condon state increases so that the non-radiative transition is decreased, resulting in the enhancement of the ICT emission. This interpretation was rationalized on the basis that a part of the DMABN molecule entrapped in the cavity is exposed to a polar solvent such as water so that the excited TICT interaction with water is not completely suppressed. In contrast, if DMABN molecule

is located entirely inside the cavity, the TICT interaction can be totally inhibited and the TICT emission is not expected to occur. Furthermore, the restrictive environment of the CD's is known to affect the excited state geometry change¹²⁻¹⁴ which is closely related to the formation of the excited TICT state. Thus, there still remain several arguments on whether the TICT emission is always enhanced upon formation of any CD complex and how the excited state geometry change is influenced by the CD complex formation. From this point of view, it would be interesting to see how the CD systems affect the TICT (ICT) emission and the excited state geometry change of a different type of TICT molecule¹⁵⁻²⁵.

Further, if the guest molecule is embedded in the hydrophobic cavity of CD, both the ICT and the excited-state geometry would be greatly affected. Also, it is possible for the phenyl moiety to be entirely entrapped in the CDs cavities in contrast to other molecules such as DMABN. From this point of view, the relation between the ICT property of 3,5-dihydroxybenzoic acid (DHBA) and 3,4,5-trihydroxybenzoic acid (THBA) is investigating in α -CD, β -CD, HP- α -CD and HP- β -CD effects on the photophysical properties of both guests in aqueous

solution. By taking advantage of environment-dependent spectral shifts of these molecules, we have probed successfully the mean structural properties of solvents, pH and β -CD¹⁵⁻²⁵. In this paper, we analysed the effect of α -CD, β -CD, HP- α -CD and HP- β -CD on the absorption and fluorescence spectra of DHBA and THBA in different pHs (pH ~ 1, pH ~ 7 and pH ~ 10).

Experimental

Reagents and methods :

DHBA, THBA, α -CD, β -CD, HP- α -CD and HP- β -CD were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich and used as such. Solutions in the pH range 2.5–12.0 were prepared by adding appropriate amount of phosphate buffer (NaOH and H₃PO₄). Hammett acidity function values are used for pH ~ 1 solution; i.e. 0.1 M H₂SO₄ are used. Triply distilled water was used for the preparation of aqueous solutions. The solutions were prepared just before taking measurements. The concentration of the guest solutions were in the order of 4×10^{-4} to 4×10^{-5} M. The concentrations of CDs were varied from 1×10^{-3} to 10×10^{-3} M. The experiments were carried out at room temperature 303 K. The solid inclusion complex is prepared by coprecipitation method.

Instruments :

Absorption spectral measurements were carried out with a Shimadzu (model UV 1601) UV-Visible spectrophotometer and fluorescence measurements were made by using a Shimadzu spectrofluorimeter (model RF-5301). The pH values in the range 2.5–12.0 were measured on an Elico pH meter (model LI-120). The fluorescence lifetime measurements were performed using a picoseconds laser and single photon counting setup from Jobin-Vyon IBH. FT-IR spectra were obtained on Avatar-330 FT-IR spectroscopy using KBr pelleting in the range 500–4000 cm⁻¹. Bruker Advance DRX 400 MHz super conducting NMR spectrophotometer was used to record ¹H NMR spectra.

Molecular modeling :

The theoretical calculations were performed with Gaussian 03W package. The initial geometry of the HBs, α -CD and β -CD were constructed with Spartan 08 and then optimized by PM3 (Parametric method 3). Both CDs were fully optimized by PM3 without any symmetry con-

straint²¹⁻²³. The glycosidic oxygen atoms of CD were placed onto the XY plane and their centre was defined as the centre of the coordination system. The primary hydroxyl groups were placed pointing toward the positive Z axis. The inclusion complexes were constructed from the PM3-optimized the CD and the guest molecules. The longer dimension of the guest molecule was initially placed onto the Z axis. The position of the guest was determined by the Z coordinate of one selected atom of the guest. The inclusion process was simulated by putting the guest in one end of CD and then letting it pass through the CD cavity. Since Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations are expensive (cost and takes long time) in treating such large molecular systems, we used single point energy calculations to the PM3 optimized geometries using semiempirical method as implemented in Gaussian 03W²¹⁻²³.

Results and discussion

Effect of cyclodextrins :

The absorption and fluorescence spectral maxima of DHBA and THBA (2×10^{-4} M) in pH ~ 1, pH ~ 7 and pH ~ 10 solutions in different α -CD, β -CD, HP- α -CD and HP- β -CD concentrations are shown in Tables 1 and 2 and Figs. 1 to 4. We provide α -CD and β -CD spectra only in the Figures and Tables, because the spectral shifts and shapes of the guests with HP- α -CD and HP- β -CD inclusion complexes were similar to the α -CD and β -CD inclusion complexes respectively. The absorbance of both molecules measured as a function of α -CD or β -CD were plotted in the inset of Figs. 1 to 4. Both compounds exist as monoanion in pH ~ 7 and dianion in pH ~ 10 buffer medium. Hence, we also recorded neutral spectrum in pH ~ 1. In absence and presence of α -CD, β -CD, HP- α -CD and HP- β -CD solutions, the absorption spectral shape of both HBAs differs in the pH ~ 1 and pH ~ 7 and pH ~ 10 buffer solutions.

The absorption maxima of DHBA at pH ~ 1 appear at 306, 249 nm, at pH ~ 7 the maximum appears at 296, 243 nm and at pH ~ 10 the maximum appears at 314, 225 nm. Upon increasing the CD concentration, in pH ~ 1 and pH ~ 7 the absorption maxima of DHBA solutions were red shifted while no significant shifts were noticed at pH ~ 10. In both β -CDs solutions, the absorbance of DHBA increased at pH ~ 7 whereas it decreased at pH ~ 1

Table 1. Absorption and fluorescence maxima of DHBA with different α -CD and β -CD concentrations

Concentration of α and β -CD (<i>M</i>)	α -CD/HP- α -CD						β -CD/HP- β -CD					
	pH ~ 1		pH ~ 7		pH ~ 10		pH ~ 1		pH ~ 7		pH ~ 10	
	λ_{abs}	$\log \epsilon$	λ_{flu}	$\log \epsilon$	λ_{abs}	$\log \epsilon$	λ_{flu}	$\log \epsilon$	λ_{abs}	$\log \epsilon$	λ_{flu}	$\log \epsilon$
0 (without CD)	271.2	3.78	367	3.92	343	3.46	447	3.78	3.92	342	3.46	449
	216.0	4.26	450	4.38	259.22	3.69	19.1	216.0	4.38	262.2	3.69	217.4
0.002	270.6	3.80	367	3.95	360	3.47	447	3.76	3.90	352	3.43	443
	216.2	4.28	450	4.40	259.2	3.70	219.3	216.0	4.23	450	3.68	219.0
0.01	270.2	3.91	367	4.13	362	3.54	447	3.64	3.80	365	3.30	443
	215.4	4.40	450	4.48	260.4	3.80	218.5	217.4	4.11	450	3.55	219.4
Excitation wavelength	280		280		350		350	280		280		350
K (1 : 1) M^{-1}	185		955		212		394			615		1482
ΔG (kJ mol^{-1})	13.15		17.28		16.50		15.0			16.27		18.44
(-ve)												

Table 2. Absorption and fluorescence maxima of THBA with different α -CD, β -CD concentrations

Concentration of α and β -CD (<i>M</i>)	α -CD/HP- α -CD						β -CD/HP- β -CD					
	pH ~ 1		pH ~ 7		pH ~ 10		pH ~ 1		pH ~ 7		pH ~ 10	
	λ_{abs}	$\log \epsilon$	λ_{flu}	$\log \epsilon$	λ_{abs}	$\log \epsilon$	λ_{flu}	$\log \epsilon$	λ_{abs}	$\log \epsilon$	λ_{flu}	$\log \epsilon$
0 (without CD)	305.4	3.36	385	4.12	353	3.14	418	3.36	4.12	353	3.14	418
	249.4	3.78	352	4.40	224.5	4.22	388s	249.2	4.40	352s	4.22	222.62
0.002	307.6	3.38	410s	4.15	410s	3.13	417	3.39	4.10	410s	3.12	420
	249.4	3.81	379	4.42	362	4.20	388s	250.2	4.38	375	4.19	223.0
				4.45	216.6							
0.01	309.8	3.46	410s	4.21	410s	3.02	417	3.49	3.98	410s	3.01	423
	250.5	3.87	379	4.49	378	4.07	388s	251.6	4.25	380	4.06	23.8
				4.55	217.4							
Excitation wavelength	300		300		310		310	300		300		310
K (1 : 1) M^{-1}	227		1485		641		1188			1239		567
ΔG (kJ mol^{-1})	13.66		18.38		15.54		17.83			17.93		15.97
(-ve)												

Fig. 1. Absorption and fluorescence spectra of DHBA in different α -CD concentrations (M) at pH \sim 1, pH \sim 7 and pH \sim 10 : (1) 0, (2) 0.002, (3) 0.004, (4) 0.006, (5) 0.008 and (6) 0.01. Insert Figure : absorbance vs $[\alpha\text{-CD}]$.

and pH \sim 10. However, in both α -CDs, the absorbance increased in the above said pH solutions. At pH \sim 10, with increase of all the four CDs concentrations, gradual decrease in the absorbance at the same wavelength was noticed.

In THBA, at pH \sim 1 the absorption maxima appear at 271, 216 nm, at pH \sim 7 appear at 259, 213 nm and at pH \sim 10 appear at 341, 259, 219 nm. With an increasing the CDs concentrations, the absorption maxima of THBA were red shifted in pH \sim 7 solutions, whereas no significant absorption spectral shifts were noticed at pH \sim 1 and pH \sim 10. In both β -CDs solutions the absorbance decreased

at pH \sim 7 and pH \sim 1, whereas increased in α -CDs. At pH \sim 10, with increase of β -CDs concentrations, gradual decrease in the absorbance at the same wavelength was noticed.

With an addition of CDs, the gradual change in the absorbance has been attributed to the enhanced dissolution of both HBA molecules indicating the formation of HBA/CDs inclusion complexes. In higher CDs concentrations, the absorption maxima and the spectral shape of HBAs in pH \sim 1 and pH \sim 7 solutions are the same which suggests similar inclusion complexes. A clear isosbestic point is present in all the three pH solutions which reveal

Fig. 2. Absorption and fluorescence spectra of DHBA in different β -CD concentrations (M) at pH \sim 1, pH \sim 7 and pH \sim 10 : (1) 0, (2) 0.002, (3) 0.004, (4) 0.006, (5) 0.008 and (6) 0.01. Insert Figure : absorbance vs $[\beta$ -CD].

that well defined 1 : 1 inclusion complexes are formed¹⁵⁻²⁵.

Figs. 1 to 4 depict the emission spectra of DHBA and THBA at pH \sim 1, pH \sim 7 and pH \sim 10 with various concentrations of α -CD, β -CD, HP- α -CD and HP- β -CD. The effect of β -CDs on the fluorescence spectra of both HBAs was more pronounced than the corresponding effect on the α -CDs. In aqueous CD free solutions, the emission maxima of these pH solutions were different from each other. With increasing both α -CD concentrations, the emission intensities increased with red shift as noticed at pH \sim 1 and pH \sim 7, while at pH \sim 10, the emis-

sion intensities increased at the same wavelength. Upon increase in the both β -CDs concentrations, at pH \sim 1 and pH \sim 10 the shorter wavelength (SW) emission intensities regularly increased at the same wavelength whereas at pH \sim 7, the SW emission was red shifted from 353 nm to 380 nm. At pH \sim 1 and pH \sim 7 a shoulder appeared in the longer wavelength (LW) at 410 nm. In contrary at pH \sim 10, the emission maximum of DHBA decreased at the same wavelength. Interestingly, in higher CDs concentrations, as in the absorption spectra, the emission maximum and the spectral shape of both pH \sim 1 and pH \sim 7 solutions

Fig. 3. Absorption and fluorescence spectra of THBA in different α -CD concentrations (M) at pH ~1, pH ~7 and pH ~10 : (1) 0, (2) 0.002, (3) 0.004, (4) 0.006, (5) 0.008 and (6) 0.01. Insert Figure : absorbance vs $[\alpha\text{-CD}]$.

were the same which indicates similar inclusion complexes formation.

Figs. 3 and 4 depict the emission spectra of THBA at pH ~1, pH ~7 and pH ~10 with various concentrations of α -CDs and β -CDs. In aqueous solution, single emission maximum was observed in all the pHs (pH ~1 : $\lambda_{\text{flu}} \sim 366$ nm; pH ~7 : $\lambda_{\text{flu}} \sim 342$ nm and pH ~10 : $\lambda_{\text{flu}} \sim 449$ nm). In both α -CDs, at pH ~1 and pH ~10, the emission maximum of THBA increased at the same wavelength whereas a red shift was noticed at pH ~7. On contrary, increasing the both β -CDs concentration the typical dual emission can be seen at pH ~1 ($\lambda_{\text{flu}} \sim 366$,

450 nm) and pH ~7 ($\lambda_{\text{flu}} \sim 365$, 450 nm). An addition to both β -CDs at pH ~1, the shorter wavelength (SW : $\lambda_{\text{flu}} \sim 365$ nm) and the longer wavelength (LW : $\lambda_{\text{flu}} \sim 450$ nm) emission intensities gradually enhanced at the same wavelength. In contrast at pH ~7, the SW emission maximum red shifted regularly ($\lambda_{\text{flu}} \sim 342$ nm to 365 nm) and the emission intensities decreased whereas the LW ($\lambda_{\text{flu}} \sim 450$ nm) emission intensities gradually increased at the same wavelength. More interestingly, like absorption spectra, with higher β -CD concentrations, the emission maxima and the spectral shape of pH ~1 and pH ~7 are same. At pH ~10, the dual fluorescence was not ob-

Fig. 4. Adsorption and fluorescence spectra of THBA in different β -CD concentrations (M) at pH ~ 1 , pH ~ 7 and pH ~ 10 : (1) 0, (2) 0.002, (3) 0.004, (4) 0.006, (5) 0.008 and (6) 0.01. Insert Figure : fluorescence intensity vs $[\beta\text{-CD}]$.

served. However, the emission intensities increased at 445 nm, while at 520 nm, the emission intensities decreased.

In the three pH solutions, the presence of isosbestic point in the absorption spectra suggests the formation of 1 : 1 inclusion complex between the guests and CDs. However, the absorption and emission spectra of both benzoic acids at pH ~ 1 and pH ~ 7 were different from pH ~ 10 indicating at least two kinds of inclusion complexes existing in all these systems. In order to determine the stoichiometry of the inclusion complexes, the dependence of the HBAs on CDs, absorbance and fluorescence

were analysed using the Benesi-Hildebrand equation²⁶ for 1 : 1 inclusion complex and the 1 : 2 complex between the HBAs and CDs. The ' K ' values were obtained from the slope and the intercept of the plots shown in Figs. 5 to 8. A plot of $1/I - I_0$ versus $1/[\text{CD}]^2$ (both absorption and fluorescence) gives an upward curves as shown in Figs. 5 to 8. However, a plot of $1/I - I_0$ versus $1/[\text{CD}]$ reveals a linear relationship. This analysis reflects the formation of 1 : 1 inclusion complex between HBA and CD complex. As can be seen from the Tables 1 and 2, ΔG is negative which suggests that the inclusion proceeded spontaneously and that the inclusion reaction of CD with guest molecule is an exothermic process.

Fig. 5. Benesi-Hildebrand plot for the complexation of DHBA and THBA with α -CD at different pH. (a) and (b) Plot of $1/A - A_0$ vs $1/[\alpha\text{-CD}]$, (c) and (d) Plot of $1/I - I_0$ vs $1/[\alpha\text{-CD}]$.

Fig. 6. Benesi-Hildebrand plot for the complexation of DHBA and THBA with β -CD at different pH. (a) and (b) Plot of $1/A - A_0$ vs $1/[\beta\text{-CD}]$, (c) and (d) Plot of $1/I - I_0$ vs $1/[\beta\text{-CD}]$.

Fig. 7. Benesi-Hildebrand plot for the complexation of DHBA and THBA with α -CD at different pH. (a) and (b) Plot of $1/A - A_0$ vs $1/[\alpha\text{-CD}]^2$, (c) and (d) Plot of $1/I - I_0$ vs $1/[\alpha\text{-CD}]^2$.

Fig. 8. Benesi-Hildebrand plot for the complexation of DHBA and THBA with β -CD at different pH. (a) and (b) Plot of $1/A - A_0$ vs $1/[\beta\text{-CD}]^2$, (c) and (d) Plot of $1/I - I_0$ vs $1/[\beta\text{-CD}]^2$.

The reason for ICT emission observed in pH ~ 1 and pH ~ 7 solutions, and this ICT emission is not observed at pH ~ 10 is explained in our earlier publications^{17,18}. The above results indicate that as long as the carboxyl group is present in the hydrophilic part, the magnitude of the contribution of the fast relaxations process to form the ICT state in the CD inclusion complex increases. The smaller size and presence of different anionic species of both HBAs are responsible for the formation of different inclusion complexes in the CD solutions. Considering that TICT emission was observed in aminobenzoic acids¹⁶, it can be concluded that the restriction or the increased viscosity in the CDs cavities does not affect the formation of the ICT state.

In α -CD and β -CD, the difference encapsulation in the inclusion process is also responsible for the varying association constants. The large association constant at pH ~ 1 and pH ~ 7 implies that HBAs were more deeply embedded in the CDs cavity than at pH ~ 10. The gradual enhancement in the ICT emission with increasing CDs concentrations is consistent with this speculation. In other words, at pH ~ 1 and pH ~ 7, both HBAs were more deeply entrapped in the non-polar CDs cavities than at pH ~ 10. Thus, the enhancement of the ICT emission in both pH ~ 1

and pH ~ 7 solutions indicates that the energy barrier is not affected by the entrapment of both HBAs in the non-polar CDs cavities. From this observation, it can be concluded that the energy barrier for the formation of the ICT state is governed by the hydrogen bonding between the carboxyl group and water. As long as the H-bonding between the carboxyl group and water is effective, the energy barrier for the ICT is not changed. As discussed above, the orientation of both HBAs inclusion complexes at pH ~ 1 and pH ~ 7 is different from that at pH ~ 10.

Fluorescence lifetime :

We have recorded the fluorescence lifetime of neutral (N), monoanion (MA) and dianion (DA) of DHBA/THBA in aqueous and CD environments (Table 3). In all the buffer solutions, the fluorescence lifetimes exhibit triexponential in water and CD medium. The dianion of DHBA/THBA has higher fluorescence lifetimes compared to neutral and monoanion. The fluorescence decay behavior of both molecules in water and CD environments are triexponential fit could yield acceptable results and such behavior may be attributed to the possible existence of different species i.e. locally excited molecule (LE), hydrogen bonded and intramolecular charge transfer (ICT).

Table 3. Fluorescence lifetime parameters of THBA and DHBA in water and α - and β -cyclodextrins

Compd.	CDs	Lifetime (ns)			Pre-exponential factor			$\langle \tau \rangle$
		τ_1	τ_2	τ_3	a_1	a_2	a_3	
DHBA	N	0.22	1.21	7.62	11.26	34.54	54.20	1.43
	N- α -CD	0.24	1.40	7.76	15.45	38.65	45.90	1.49
	N- β -CD	0.28	1.55	8.02	16.12	41.57	42.31	1.55
	MA	0.16	0.87	3.23	14.34	22.65	63.01	0.98
	MA- α -CD	0.18	0.91	3.46	16.45	32.22	51.33	1.03
	MA- β -CD	0.21	1.05	3.51	17.45	36.89	45.66	1.11
	DA	0.11	0.76	9.22	5.63	23.89	70.48	1.87
	DA- α -CD	0.16	0.79	9.56	6.57	28.21	65.22	1.94
	DA- β -CD	0.19	0.83	10.90	7.02	30.55	62.43	2.05
THBA	N	0.46	1.52	8.22	8.90	25.87	65.23	2.65
	N- α -CD	0.49	1.57	8.36	9.21	34.24	56.55	2.68
	N- β -CD	0.51	1.61	8.45	9.45	41.20	50.65	2.74
	MA	0.25	1.08	2.98	16.45	60.76	22.79	1.65
	MA- α -CD	0.26	1.16	3.21	18.67	56.34	24.99	1.67
	MA- β -CD	0.28	1.23	3.28	20.24	46.76	33.00	1.75
	DA	0.17	1.11	9.57	7.65	24.90	67.45	2.56
	DA- α -CD	0.17	1.14	9.64	9.76	31.98	58.26	2.59
	DA- β -CD	0.19	1.18	9.78	12.87	37.65	49.48	2.66

Compared to water, the high lifetime values in CDs indicate the formation of inclusion complex. The lifetime enhancement indicates that both molecules experience hydrophobic environments with the CD cavities where non-radiative decay processes are reduced. This might be due to the variation in the microscopic environment experienced by both benzoic acid molecules in the presence of CDs solution.

Infrared spectral studies :

DHBA : The COOH group frequency appearing around 1688–1515 cm^{-1} is the vibrational absorption of carbonyl group of DHBA. The phenolic OH group appears at 1302 cm^{-1} in DHBA, whereas in the inclusion complex it is moved to 1313 cm^{-1} . The aromatic (C–H) and C–O–C and bending vibrations of OH in COOH group appear at 2926, 1407 and 1163 cm^{-1} , respectively and in the inclusion complex it is moved to 2931, 1165, 1419 cm^{-1} . The hydrogen bond frequency of DHBA appears at 3202 cm^{-1} and in the inclusion complex it is shifted to 3223 cm^{-1} . Further, the absorption intensities in the inclusion complex were significantly different from DHBA. The inclusion complex FT-IR peaks are 30–50% weaker than the free DHBA molecule which indicates DHBA is included into the cavity of CDs.

THBA : Absorption peaks of COOH group appearing around 1617–1544 cm^{-1} are the vibrational absorption of carbonyl group of THBA. The phenolic OH group appears at 1341 cm^{-1} in THBA, whereas in the inclusion complex, it is moved to 1346 cm^{-1} . The aromatic (C–H) and C–O–C and bending vibrations of OH in COOH group appear at 2955, 1457 and 1101 cm^{-1} , respectively and in the inclusion complex, it is moved to 2962, 1460 and 1106 cm^{-1} . The hydrogen bond frequency appears at 3363 cm^{-1} and in the inclusion complex, it is shifted to 3370 cm^{-1} . Further, the absorption intensities in the inclusion complex were significantly different from THBA. The inclusion complex FT-IR peaks are 30–50% weaker than the free THBA molecule which indicates THBA is included into the cavity of CD.

¹H NMR spectral studies :

Proton nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy has proved to be a powerful tool in the study of inclusion complexes²⁷. The chemical shifts values of DHBA, THBA and the inclusion complexes are given below : DHBA

(inclusion complex) (ppm) : COOH ~ 12.612 w (12.615), OH ~ 9.632w (9.643), 2H and 6H ~ 6.845w (6.849) and 4H ~ 6.457w (6.459); THBA (inclusion complex) (ppm) : 2H and 6H ~ 7.093w (7.096). The resonance assignment of the protons of the CDs is well established and consists of six types of protons. As can be seen from the values, the chemical shifts data for the inclusion complex were different from the free compound. In DHBA and THBA, the phenolic OH (H-4, -0.12 ppm) is shifted downfield in the complex, which suggests that this group is shielded largely in the complex and it must penetrate deeply into the cavity. Further, the resonance of DHBA and THBA protons with the CD cavities were shifted downfield when the inclusion complex was formed, which shows that DHBA and THBA have preferred fixed orientations with the CD cavities.

Molecular modeling :

Quantum mechanical calculations were made in order to obtain information related to the structural characteristics and thermodynamic magnitudes of the 1 : 1 complex between the neutral, monoanion and dianion species of the guests and CDs. The values used in the calculation of these magnitudes are the ones obtained in the frequency analysis carried out with the PM3 method. This analysis was performed on the structures of the inclusion complex with the lowest energy which were obtained during the simulation of the inclusion process in each one of the orientations considered. The optimized structure of all species and inclusion complexes are shown in Figs. 9 to 12 with the minimized energy structure. Consistent with the experimental results^{20–22}, the hydroxyl group of DHBA is entrapped in the interior part of the CD cavity and carboxyl group is present in the hydrophilic part of the CD cavity. In THBA, the carboxyl group is entrapped in the interior part of the CD cavity and hydroxyl group is present in the hydrophilic part of the CD cavity.

In this study we have considered only the inclusion compounds in molar proportion 1 : 1 formed between one molecule of α -CD or β -CD and one neutral (N), or monoanion (MA) or dianion (DA) species of DHBA/THBA. All the complexation energies are negative which show that the inclusion process of all the species in both α -CD and β -CD is thermodynamically favorable. Table 4 and Table 5 show the calculated binding energy of all species of DHBA/THBA complexed with α -CD and β -

Fig. 9. The inclusion complex structure of (a) DHBA-N, (b) DHBA-MA and (c) DHBA-DA with α -CD.

CD. To quantify the interaction between host and guest in the optimized geometries, we have evaluated binding energy change, which was calculated by subtracting the sum of the energy of individual free host and guest molecules to the energy of the inclusion complex.

The negative binding energy changes upon complexation clearly demonstrate that CD can form stable inclusion complexes with DHBA/THBA. The binding energy change of DHBA/THBA : β -CD is more negative than

that of DHBA/THBA : α -CD. Also, the binding energy change of dianion of DHBA/THBA : α -CD/ β -CD is more negative than the other complexes. This indicated that the complexation of CD with dianion of DHBA/THBA is stronger than that with monoanion and neutral of DHBA/THBA. All species prefer to occupy most of the available space in the cavity of CD, which is in good agreement with experimental results²⁰⁻²². The binding energy of the isolated molecule and complex suggested that stability of

Fig. 10. The inclusion complex structure of (a) DHBA-N, (b) DHBA-MA and (c) DHBA-DA with β -CD.

complex was high compared to isolated molecule.

From Table 4 and Table 5, the dipole moment of the neutral DHBA is 4.12 D, DHBA monoanion is 3.03 D, DHBA dianion is 10.72, neutral THBA is 4.01 D, THBA

monoanion is 13.03 D and THBA dianion is 5.95 D. The dipole moments of neutral and dianion complexes are significantly higher than the monoanion complexes in DHBA, whereas in THBA the dipole moment of neutral

Fig. 11. The inclusion complex structure of (a) THBA-N, (b) THBA-MA and (c) THBA-DA with α -CD.

and monoanion complexes has significantly higher value than the dianion complexes. The above quantum mechanical computation values demonstrated a strong relationship with the complexation behaviour.

From the optimized structures of the inclusion complexes, three H bond is formed between DHBA/THBA

and CDs. Hydrogen bond length is shorter than 3.0 Å which just falls within the expected data²⁸⁻³⁰. This is justified the importance of both interaction energy between the guest and host molecules necessary to ensure a better inclusion of the guest to the CD. The above values were supported by the fact that the flexibility of the host

Fig. 12. The inclusion complex structure of (a) THBA-N, (b) THBA-MA and (c) THBA-DA with β -CD.

molecule and substitutions of the guest molecules may be one of the structural requirements for inclusion complexes formation.

Frontier molecular orbitals :

The highest occupied molecular orbitals (HOMOs) and the lowest-lying unoccupied molecular orbitals (LUMOs)

are named as frontier molecular orbitals (FMOs). FMOs play an important role in the optical and electric properties, as well as in quantum chemistry and UV-Vis spectra. HOMO, LUMO and HOMO-LUMO energy gap values were presented in Table 4 and Table 5. HOMO, LUMO energy structure of all the species for both mole-

Table 4. Binding energies and HOMO, LUMO energy of neutral, monoanion and dianion of DHBA before inclusion complexation by PM3 method

Properties	N	MA	DA	N : α -CD	MA : α -CD	DA : α -CD	N : β -CD	MA : β -CD	DA : β -CD
E_{HOMO} (eV)	-9.60	-9.42	-9.12	-9.01	-6.52	-2.45	-9.11	-6.48	-2.79
E_{LUMO} (eV)	-0.75	-0.72	-4.72	-0.30	2.69	5.86	-0.54	2.69	5.41
$E_{\text{HOMO}} - E_{\text{LUMO}}$ (eV)	-8.85	-8.69	-4.39	-8.71	-9.21	-8.31	-8.57	-9.17	-8.20
Dipole (D)	4.12	3.03	10.72	8.59	5.19	6.14	8.34	4.63	9.00
ΔD				-6.87	-9.18	-15.92	-8.07	-10.68	-14.00
E^a	-155.20	-99.93	-33.82	-1410.97	-1468.23	-1460.96	-1623.49	-1682.07	-1688.73
ΔE^a				-8.25	-120.78	-179.62	-10.66	-124.51	-197.28
H^a	69.22	24.33	33.43	-766.21	-824.15	-822.05	-882.80	-941.69	-953.08
ΔH^a				-293.35	-304.05	-296.47	-313.60	-325.25	-331.88
G^a	98.35	51.11	45.63	-646.72	-710.90	-713.01	-746.76	-811.67	-826.49
ΔG^*				-39.21	-58.50	-69.71	-26.46	-46.48	-70.40
S^b	0.097	0.089	0.096	0.400	0.379	0.365	0.456	0.436	0.424
ΔS^b				0.753	0.732	0.718	0.768	0.756	0.737
Zero point energy	79.26	69.97	60.69	715.43	710.26	702.11	820.69	816.12	809.21
Mullikan charges	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-1.00	-2.00	0	-1	-2

Unit : a kcal mol $^{-1}$, b kcal/mol-Kelvin.**Table 5.** Binding energies and HOMO, LUMO energy of neutral, monoanion and dianion of THBA before inclusion complexation by PM3 method

Properties	N	MA	DA	N : α -CD	MA : α -CD	DA : α -CD	N : β -CD	MA : β -CD	DA : β -CD
E_{HOMO} (eV)	-9.49	-4.61	0.37	-9.15	-6.55	-2.28	-9.37	-6.72	-2.85
E_{LUMO} (eV)	-0.62	3.63	8.38	-0.25	2.53	5.85	-0.39	2.81	6.41
$E_{\text{HOMO}} - E_{\text{LUMO}}$ (eV)	-8.86	-8.25	-8.01	-8.90	-9.09	-8.13	-9.76	-9.53	9.26
Dipole (D)	4.01	13.03	5.95	10.53	15.04	7.19	11.57	13.21	7.65
ΔD				-4.82	-9.33	-10.09	-6.66	-12.11	-10.59
E^a	-196.78	-223.59	-182.97	-1441.43	-1493.26	-1496.48	-1657.91	-1697.24	-1711.25
ΔE^a				-2.87	-22.15	-65.99	-3.50	-16.02	-70.95
H^a	107.18	143.63	110.50	-792.34	-844.02	-854.50	-915.29	-974.12	-984.32
ΔH^a				-360.01	-445.54	-423.92	-386.62	-479.30	-457.40
G^a	138.88	172.73	140.63	-673.75	-732.40	-745.24	-776.98	-844.71	-857.28
ΔG^a				-104.20	-199.30	-179.01	-94.64	-198.82	-181.26
S^b	0.106	0.097	0.101	0.397	0.374	0.368	0.463	0.428	0.409
ΔS^b				0.644	0.630	0.620	0.766	0.739	0.717
Zero point energy	81.70	73.13	65.52	718.67	713.82	705.48	823.98	807.43	799.08
Mullikan charges	0.00	0.00	0.00			-2	0	-1	-2

Unit : a kcal mol $^{-1}$, b kcal/mol-Kelvin.

cules is described in Fig. 13. HOMO represents the ability to donate an electron, LUMO as an electron acceptor represents the ability to obtain an electron. The energy gap between HOMO and LUMO determines the kinetic stability, chemical reactivity and optical polarizability and chemical hardness-softness of a molecule²⁰⁻²². HOMO-LUMO values of the inclusion complexes are more nega-

tive than the free guests. This suggests that inclusion complexes are more stable than the isolated guests. In fact, with the increase of the ($E_{\text{HOMO}} - E_{\text{LUMO}}$) gap for the complexes, a new confirmation. However, the energy gap between HOMO and LUMO of each complex suggested that these will be no significant change in the electronic spectrum of the guest molecules driving molecular

Fig. 13. HOMO-LUMO energy structure of (a) DHBA-N, (b) DHBA-MA, (c) DHBA-DA, (d) THBA-N, (e) THBA-MA and (f) THBA-DA.

recognition and binding.

Thermodynamic parameters :

The statistical thermodynamic calculations were performed using Harmonic frequency analysis in PM3 method for the most stable structures, characterizing them as true minima on the potential energy surface. The frequencies analyses were then used for the evaluation of the thermo-

dynamic parameters, such as enthalpy changes (ΔH), entropy contribution (ΔS) and Gibbs free energy (ΔG), for the statistical thermodynamic parameters in binding process of DHBA/THBA with both CDs at 298 K at 1 atm summarized in Tables 4 and 5. It can be observed that the inclusion complexation of both acids with CDs are exothermic judged from the negative enthalpy changes. The

energy, enthalpy and free energy change for the DHBA : β -CD inclusion complexes are more negative than that for the other complexes. It means that all the inclusion processes are enthalpically favorable in nature due to the negative enthalpy changes. The ΔH and ΔS in the inclusion process of the all complexes with CD to form the most stable complexes are negative, suggesting that the formation of the inclusion complex is an enthalpy-driven process. Further, the negative ΔG was obtained for all molecules that were investigated (DHBA, THBA), which implies that the inclusion complexation reaction between all the species and CDs proceeds spontaneously. Binding of all molecules with CDs is enthalpy-entropy favourable showing negative ΔH and ΔS values.

In Tables 6 and 7 we report the selected bond distances, bond angles and the most interesting angles between the hydroxyl group and phenyl ring of these molecules before and after complexation as calculated by PM3 method for the most stable inclusion complex. From comparison of free guests and the complexes, it is clear that the geometrical structure of the guests after complexation is completely altered. This alteration was achieved through the variation of the dihedral angles between the phenyl ring and the COOH and OH functional groups of these guests which was subject to a distortion to adopt a specific conformation leading to the formation of a most stable complex. The non-bonded interaction between the phenyl ring and CD might be responsible for the difference in structure stability of the complex. Experimental thermodynamical values will be helpful for numerical investigations in order to draw a conclusion about the effect of the solvent on the binding of the complexation.

Charge transfer interaction :

The charge transfer interactions play an important role in the stabilization of the inclusion complexes. The Mullikan charges of the heavy atoms of all species of DHBA/THBA charge transfer of the models are summarized in Tables 4 and 5. The data show that the CD molecules accept the electron from DHBA/THBA. From the tables, the carbonyl oxygen atoms of monoanion and dianion species of DHBA/THBA in CDs are significantly changed in the electron density compared to neutral DHBA/THBA in CD. Mullikan charge distribution analysis reveals that in the complexes, α -CD and β -CD as a whole always obtains a nontrivial negative charge. Thus, charge-

Table 6. Geometrical parameters of neutral (N), monoanion (MA) and dianion (DA) of DHBA before and after inclusion in α -CD and β -CD for the most stable inclusion complexes

Properties	N	N : α -CD	N : β -CD	MA	MA : α -CD	MA : β -CD	DA	DA : α -CD	DA : β -CD
Bond length (Å)									
	H1-H4	5.86	5.88	C7-C4	4.30	4.31	C7-C4	4.30	4.31
	C7-C4	4.30	4.32	H4-H2	5.55	5.56	O3-O4	4.76	4.77
	O3-O4	4.77	4.79	O3-O4	4.77	4.79	O1-O4	5.10	5.11
	H5-H3	5.55	5.57	O1-O4	5.08	5.12	O2-O3	5.18	5.19
	O2-O3	5.23	5.19	O2-O3	5.19	5.21			
Bond angle (°)									
	O1-C7-O2	110	112	O1-C7-O2	111	112	O1-C7-O2	110	111
	C7-C1-C2	118	119	C7-C1-C2	118	122	C7-C1-C2	120	118
	O3-C3-C2	122	121	O3-C3-C2	122	120	O3-C3-C2	119	119
Dihedral angle (°)									
	O1-C7-C6-C5	0	-0.20	O1-C7-C6-C5	0	-0.16	O1-C7-C6-C5	0	-0.19
	O2-C7-C1-C2	0	-1.29	O2-C7-C1-C2	0	-1.25	O2-C7-C1-C2	0	-1.22
	O3-C3-C4-C5	180	176	O3-C3-C4-C5	180	178	O3-C3-C4-C5	180	178

Table 7. Geometrical parameters of neutral (N), monoanion (MA) and dianion (DA) of THBA before and after inclusion in α -CD and β -CD for the most stable inclusion complexes

Properties	N	N : α -CD	N : β -CD	MA	MA : α -CD	MA : β -CD	DA	DA : α -CD	DA : β -CD
Bond length (Å)									
	O1-O4	6.44	6.45	O1-O4	6.44	6.43	O1-O4	6.44	6.45
	C7-C4	4.28	4.30	C7-C4	4.27	4.30	C7-C4	4.29	4.31
	O3-O5	4.84	4.83	O3-O5	4.81	4.82	O3-O5	4.80	4.82
	H1-H4	6.68	6.71	H2-H4	5.62	5.61	H2-H3	5.65	5.63
	H3-H5	5.61	5.62						
Bond angle (°)									
	O1-C7-O2	110	109	O1-C7-O2	112	112	O1-C7-O2	110	111
	C7-C1-C2	118	119	C7-C1-C2	120	122	C7-C1-C2	118	118
	O3-C3-C2	122	123	O3-C3-C2	120	120	O3-C3-C2	119	119
	O1-C7-O2	110	109	O1-C7-O2	112	112			
Dihedral angle (°)									
	O3-C3-C4-O4	-0.94	-0.92	O3-C3-C4-O4	-0.91	-0.93	O3-C3-C4-O4	-0.87	-0.90
	O1-C7-C6-C5	0	-0.11	O1-C7-C6-C5	-0.16	-0.17	O1-C7-C6-C5	0	-0.19
	C1-C2-C3-C4	0.03	0.03	C1-C2-C3-C4	0.03	0.03	C1-C2-C3-C4	0.03	0.03

transfer takes place in CD complexation. In the present systems, CD is a Lewis acid accepting electrons, while the guest compounds act as Lewis bases donating electrons. From Tables 1 and 2, the complexation energy for dianion of DHBA/THBA is significantly favoured than the neutral and monoanion of DHBA/THBA.

The most important term in the charge-transfer energy comes from the interaction of the HOMO of the guest compounds and the LUMO of α -CD. The higher HOMO values of the guest molecule indicates the charge-transfer interaction is stronger in the complexation. As the HOMO of dianion of DHBA/THBA lies significantly higher than that of neutral and monoanion of DHBA/THBA, stronger charge-transfer interaction will take place in dianion of DHBA/THBA than in monoanion of DHBA/THBA, and neutral DHBA/THBA. As a result, though dianion of DHBA/THBA is more hydrophilic and has a smaller dipole moment than monoanion of DHBA/THBA, and neutral DHBA/THBA, CD complexation with the former can be more favorable than that with the latter.

It should be mentioned that the above comparison of the strength of charge-transfer interaction is only useful when the guest molecules are isoelectronic. Otherwise, factors such as dipole moments and steric effect can greatly affect the stability of the complexes, which makes the comparison of charge transfer interaction less meaningful. Apparently, though charge transfer interaction is shown to be a driving force in CD complexation and can determine the strength of complexation for isoelectronic guest molecules, it is not expected to be a major driving force in CD complexation as shown by the small Mullikan charge transferred from the guest to the host.

Conclusions

Based on the above discussion we conclude the following points : (i) in pH ~ 1, pH ~ 7 and pH ~ 10 solutions both HBAs form 1 : 1 inclusion complex, (ii) the entrapment of both HBAs in the four CDs cause ICT emission at pH ~ 1 and pH ~ 7, (iii) the ratio of ICT emission to the normal emission of both HBAs at pH ~ 7 increases on increasing the concentration of CD, where as this ratio is constant at pH ~ 1 and (iv) at pH ~ 10, the hydroxyl anion and IPT prevents ICT emission. The hydrogen bonding interactions of the electron withdrawing group with water plays an important role in controlling

the ICT process in aqueous CD solutions.

The complexation of neutral, monoanion and dianion species of both guests with α -CD and β -CD was studied by PM3 method. From the above study we find that (i) the inclusion structure of the six inclusion complexes was different, (ii) all the three species (N, MA, DA) were partially encapsulated into the CD cavity, (iii) the negative Gibbs energy and enthalpy changes for the inclusion complexes indicated that the formation of these complexes was spontaneous and exothermic, (iv) hydrogen bonding interactions played a major role in the inclusion process, (v) the dipole moment values for guests increased when they entered into the CD cavity which is an indication of the increase of the polarity and the formation of complexes, (vi) the computational results indicated that the formation of all the inclusion complexes was enthalpy driven process and (vii) the complexation of dianion species of DHBA/THBA gave more stable complexes and the charge transfer interaction was more favorable for dianion : CD inclusion complexes.

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References

1. J. Szejtli, "Cyclodextrin Technology", Kluwer Academic Publisher, Dordrecht, 1988.
2. M. L. Bender and H. Komiyama, "Cyclodextrin Chemistry", Springer Verlag, New York, 1978.
3. K. Kalyanasundaram, "Photochemistry in Microheterogeneous System", Academic Press, New York, 1987.
4. M. Hoshino, M. Imamura, K. Ikahara and Y. Hama, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1981, **85**, 1820.
5. N. Thuaud, N.-M. Gosselet, B. Sebillé, N. Veyron and P. Tachon, *J. Incl. Phenom. Macrocycl. Chem.*, 1996, **25**, 267.
6. I. R. Politzer, K. T. Crago, T. Hampton, J. Joseph, J. H. Boyer and M. Shah, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1989, **159**, 258.
7. P. Bortolus and S. Monti, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1987, **91**, 5046.
8. G. L. Duveneck, E. V. Sitzmann, K. B. Eisenthal and N. J. Turro, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1989, **93**, 7166.
9. M. Itoh and V. Fujiwara, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1984, **57**, 2261.
10. T. Yorozu, H. Hoshino and M. Imamura, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1982, **86**, 4426.
11. A. Nag, R. Dutta, N. Chattopadhyay and K. Bhattacharyya, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1989, **157**, 83.
12. Y.-Q. Zhai, S.-Z. Zhang, J.-W. Xie and C.-S. Liu, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2003, **494**, 71.
13. S. Monti, L. Flamigni, A. Martelli and P. Bortolus, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1988, **92**, 4447.
14. R. A. Agbaria, R. Uzan and D. Gill, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1989, **93**, 3855.
15. N. Rajendiran and T. Balasubramanian, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 2007, **68**, 894.
16. T. Stalin and N. Rajendiran, *Chem. Phys.*, 2006, **322**, 311.
17. R. K. Sankaranarayanan, S. Siva, A. Antony Muthu Prabhu and N. Rajendiran, *J. Incl. Phenom. Macrocycl. Chem.*, 2010, **67**, 461.
18. S. Siva, R. K. Sankaranarayanan, A. Antony Muthu Prabhu and N. Rajendiran, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2009, **48**, 1515.
19. N. Rajendiran and T. Balasubramanian, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 2007, **68**, 867.
20. A. Antony Muthu Prabhu, R. K. Sankaranarayanan, S. Siva and N. Rajendiran, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 2009, **74**, 484.
21. M. Jude Jenita, G. Venkatesh and N. Rajendiran, *J. Mol. Liq.*, 2013, **78**, 160.
22. A. A. M. Prabhu, R. K. Sankaranarayanan, G. Venkatesh and N. Rajendiran, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 2012, **116**, 9061.
23. S. Siva and N. Rajendiran, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 2013, **115**, 559.
24. A. Antony Muthu Prabhu, R. K. Sankaranarayanan, S. Siva, V. K. Subramanian and N. Rajendiran, *Russian J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2010, **84**, 2270.
25. A. Antony Muthu Prabhu, G. Venkatesh and N. Rajendiran, *J. Soln. Chem.*, 2010, **39**, 1061.
26. H. A. Benesi and J. H. Hildebrand, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 2703.
27. M. C. Rath, D. K. Palit and T. Mukherjee, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1998, **94**, 1189.
28. A. A. Rafati, S. M. Hashemianzadeh, Z. B. Nojini and M. A. Safarpour, *J. Mol. Liq.*, 2007, **135**, 153.
29. L. Seridi and A. Boufelfel, *J. Mol. Liq.*, 2011, **158**, 15.
30. T. Sivasankar, A. A. M. Prabhu, M. Karthick and N. Rajendiran, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 2012, **1028**, 57.